

EMPLOYING TESTING ASSESSMENTS: READING AND WRITING FOR SIMPLE AND DEAF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This study describes a testing assessment designed for threshold-level learners, focusing on reading and writing skills. The assessment incorporates various methods to evaluate both micro and macro reading skills, emphasizing skimming, scanning, and comprehension strategies. Writing assessment is aligned with the reading theme of environmental sustainability and assesses students' ability to express ideas on the topic. The chosen rubrics provide specific feedback to promote improved communication.

The assessment caters to individual needs by offering differentiated instruction for students with hearing impairments. This includes extended response time, creation of visual aids using "Visme," and strategically assigning tasks to minimize anxiety. The conclusion acknowledges the need for ongoing assessment development, particularly creating rubrics tailored to learners with diverse needs.

Keywords: productive skill, receptive skill, hearing impairment, differentiation, comprehension, rubric, analytic rubric.

Classroom profile

For this formative assignment, first-grade World Language University students have chosen. The group number is XT-2417, there are 14 students, 12 of them female and 2 of them male. Their first language is Uzbek; most are multilingual and speak Russian, Persian and Kazak. The average age is from 18 to 19, most of them are from different regions and their current level is B1 (Threshold), and the target level is B2 (Vantage). On the IELTS scale, their level is 4.5 to 5, in WIDA it will be level 3 (Developing). For the spring semester, their course is Aspects of the English Language which is one of the hard skills which they need to learn. In this course, students acquire all integrated skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing), grammar, and vocabulary. In addition to this, various methods were conducted to improve their abilities during class such as CLT, Suggestopedia and audio-lingual methods to improve all skills, and TBLT used to increase their critical thinking and oral skills. Before entering and enrolling on studies at university these students worked under GTM (Grammar Translation Method) and got only grammatical knowledge to take an entrance exam, now from this course, they will start to use both soft and hard skills. In this group, students vary from each other in their personalities,

backgrounds, and motives. “An individual’s languages are rarely socially equal. They carry different degrees of power and prestige and are used for different purposes, in different contexts, and with different interlocutors” (Garcia, 2011, p.4)

Sardor (B1 with hearing impairment): An active student with introverted tendencies but high intrinsic motivation. He excels in group work and wants to solidify his English teaching knowledge. Given his introversion, Sardor might benefit from the individual practice component more and could be encouraged to choose a topic related to teaching methodology for the discussion.

Dildora (B2): An extroverted student who enjoys group discussions and seeks to improve fluency and communication skills for a future career in translation. Dildora might flourish in the partner discussion activity, allowing her to practice actively engaging with a peer.

Madina (B1): A high-achieving ambivert who grasps grammar and linguistics quickly but hesitates to speak publicly. Madina could benefit from all components of the assessment. The self/peer assessment and instructor feedback in the practice session can help her identify areas to improve confidence. During the discussions, she can choose a familiar topic and be paired with a supportive partner.

Part 1: Reading & Vocabulary (original)

Target Skill: Reading

Secondary Skills: Vocabulary

Objectives

SWBAT:

- Understand the contemporary problems of air and water pollution.
- Pick up specific vocabularies on pollution through the article. (CEFR B2, orientation)
- Develop reading comprehension by identifying key facts in a text to evaluate the accuracy of True/False statements.

Assessment outline

You will read a short, adapted news article (515 words) about environmental sustainability from the National Geography journal. The article will be visually appealing and contain bolded key vocabulary words with definitions or pictures for context.

You should spend 30 minutes on this task.

Comprehension: True/false questions assess factual understanding of the main ideas.

Vocabulary Matching: Match the bolded words in the article to their definitions.

Article: pollution

Pollution is the introduction of *harmful* materials into the environment. These harmful materials are called *pollutants*. Pollutants can be natural, such as *volcanic ash*. They can also be created by human activity, such as trash or *runoff* produced by factories. Pollutants damage the quality of air, water, and land.

Many things that are useful to people produce pollution. Cars *spew* pollutants from their *exhaust* pipes. Burning coal to create electricity pollutes the air. Industries and homes *generate* garbage and *sewage* that can pollute the land and water. *Pesticides*—chemical poisons used to kill weeds and insects—seep into waterways and harm wildlife. All living things—from one-celled microbes to blue whales—depend on Earth’s air and water supply. When these resources are polluted, all forms of life are threatened.

Pollution is a global problem. Although *urban areas* are usually more polluted than the *countryside*, pollution can spread to *remote places* where no people live. For example, pesticides and other chemicals have been found in the Antarctic *ice sheet*. In the middle of the northern Pacific Ocean, a huge collection of *microscopic plastic particles* forms what is known as the Great Pacific Garbage Patch.

Air and water *currents* carry pollution. Ocean currents and migrating fish carry *marine* pollutants far and wide. *Winds* can pick up *radioactive* material accidentally released from a nuclear reactor and scatter it around the world. *Smoke* from a factory in one country drifts into another country.

Air Pollution

Sometimes, air pollution is *visible*. A person can see dark smoke pour from the exhaust pipes of large trucks or factories, for example. More often, however, air pollution is *invisible*. Natural disasters can also cause air pollution to increase quickly. When volcanoes *erupt*, they *eject* volcanic ash and gases into the *atmosphere*. Volcanic ash can discolour the sky for months. After the eruption of the Indonesian volcano of *Krakatoa* in 1883, ash darkened the sky around the world. The dimmer sky caused fewer *crops* to be *harvested* as far away as Europe and North America. For years, *meteorologists* tracked what was known as the “equatorial smoke stream.” In fact, this smoke *stream* was a *jet stream*, a wind high in Earth’s atmosphere that Krakatoa’s air pollution made visible.

Volcanic gases, such as *sulfur dioxide*, can kill nearby residents and make the *soil infertile* for years. Mount Vesuvius, a volcano in Italy, famously erupted in 79, killing hundreds of residents of the nearby towns of Pompeii and Herculaneum. Most victims of Vesuvius were not killed by lava or *landslides* caused by the eruption. They were choked, or *asphyxiated*, by deadly volcanic gases.

Water Pollution

Some polluted water looks muddy, smells bad, and has garbage floating in it. Some polluted water looks clean but contains harmful chemicals you can't see or smell.

Polluted water is unsafe for drinking and swimming. Some people who drink polluted water are exposed to *hazardous chemicals* that may make them sick years later. Others *consume* bacteria and other tiny *aquatic* organisms that cause disease. *The United Nations* estimates that 4,000 children die every day from drinking dirty water.

Source: <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/pollution/>

Instruction: Read each statement carefully and choose True or False based on the information in the passage.

1. Only humans can cause pollution not nature. (True / False)
2. Pollution is always visible because it's dark and smoky. (True / False)
3. Pollution can affect the quality of air, water, and land. (True / False)
4. Volcanoes always help plants grow by adding nutrients to the soil. (True / False)
5. Polluted water is sometimes visibly soft and clear however makes people sick. (True / False)
6. Air pollution and water pollution never affect each other. (True / False)
7. The eruption of Mount Vesuvius killed people with hot lava flows. (True / False)

Instruction: Match the bolded words in the article to their definitions

Volcanic gas	liquid and solid waste material from homes and businesses.
Sewage	chemical or other substance that harms a natural resource.
Runoff	gas such as water vapor or carbon dioxide that is released into the atmosphere by a volcano.
Remote	overflow of fluid from a farm or industrial factory
Pollutant	Distant or far away
Pesticide	natural or manufactured substances used to kill organisms that threaten agriculture or are undesirable.

Differentiation for disabled deaf students (reading)

Target skill: Reading

Secondary skill: Vocabulary

Assessment outline

You will read a short, adapted news article (515 words) about environmental sustainability from the National Geography journal. The article will be visually appealing and contain bolded key vocabulary words with definitions, high-quality images and infographics related to air and water pollution alongside the text.

You should spend 30 minutes on this task.

Students with learning difficulties:

Vocabulary Matching: Match the bolded words in the article to their definitions with the help of infographics and images.

For simple students:

Comprehension: True/false questions assess factual understanding of the main ideas.

Instruction: Match the bolded words in the article to their definitions

VOLCANIC GAS		LIQUID AND SOLID WASTE MATERIAL FROM HOMES AND BUSINESSES.
Sewage		chemical or other substance that harms a natural resource.
Runoff		gas such as water vapor or carbon dioxide that is released into the atmosphere by a volcano.
Remote		overflow of fluid from a farm or industrial factory
Pollutant		Distant or far away
Pesticide		natural or manufactured substances used to kill organisms that threaten agriculture or are undesirable.

Part 2: Writing & Grammar (original)

Target Skill: Writing

Secondary Skill: Grammar

Objectives

SWBAT:

- State an opinion between car demand and pollution to strengthen the position.

- Express ideas with specific vocabulary in rising private cars and causes.
- Write complex structures to describe cause and effect relationships in the essay

(first conditionals)

Assessment outline

Write a short mini essay expressing your opinion on “Nowadays, the demand for private cars is increasing and it has led to a rise in pollution levels in many cities.” Use the first conditional sentence structure based on the information from the reading to express ideas. Write at least 150 to 200 words.

You should spend 40 minutes on this task.

Rubric: Analytic rubric.

Descriptors & grades	Below 2	3 (fair)	4 (good)	5 (excellent)
Task response	Do not attempt the assigned task or focus on a different activity, not the opinion essay about rising cars and their causes.	Makes an effort to complete the opinion essay, but understanding may be limited. The response may be incomplete or off-topic in rising private cars and their causes.	Generally addresses the opinion essay with general ideas and keywords but may have minor deviations (e.g., missing key information, incomplete response)	Addresses the requirement of the opinion essay. Clearly presents the purpose and highlights with detailed information of rising private cars and their causes.
Coherence & cohesion	Ideas are unrelated or unclear. The connection between sentences is incomplete and lacks logic.	Ideas may be connected but loosely connected or off-topic, not related to the effects of private cars. Sentences are very simple with limited connection.	Ideas are generally related to the topic of the causes of private cars but may lack a central focus. Sentences flow somewhat logically, but connections could be improved.	Arrange information clearly on the topic of causes of private cars coherently, and use cohesive devices effectively.
Lexical resource	Uses a limited vocabulary of water and air pollution, and some of them are not appropriate for the topic and the task.	Uses non-academic vocabulary about water and air pollution for the task and uses very familiar words, synonyms and some words are repetitive.	Uses vocabulary appropriate for the task and may use some simpler synonyms or descriptive words about water and air pollution.	Uses an adequate range of vocabulary of water and air pollution. Uses sophisticated lexical items

Grammatical accuracy	It uses only simple sentences to express ideas. Did not use the first conditional sentence structure (If...). May have many grammatical and punctual errors in sentence fragments.	Uses simple sentences to express ideas. One or two first conditional sentence structures used, still have errors (If...). It may have occasional sentence fragments or errors in punctuation.	It uses a mix of simple and compound sentences to express ideas. Used first conditional sentence structure (If...). May have occasional sentence fragments or run-on sentences	It uses a mix of simple sentence forms to express ideas— grammatical accuracy and punctuation with rare minor errors. Correctly used first conditional sentence structure (If...).
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Differentiation for deaf students (writing)

Target skill: Writing

Secondary skill: Grammar

Assessment outline

You will be given cards with a task which allows you to choose your essay topic within your special day (birthday) if the task says “December” if you were born in this month you need to write on this topic. Choose the card according to your birth month.

Here are the example cards:

For low-level

Instruction

Write a short mini essay expressing your opinion on "Nowadays, the demand for private cars is increasing and it has led to a rise in pollution levels in many cities." Use **at least 2** of the first conditional sentence structures based on the information from the reading to express ideas. Write at least 150 to 200 words.
You should spend 40 minutes on this task.

*if you were born in **August** write a mini-essay about "causes and results of air and water pollution"

For high-level

Instruction

Write a short mini essay expressing your opinion on “Causes and results of air and water pollution” Use the first conditional sentence structure based on the information from the reading to express ideas. Write at least 150 to 200 words.

You should spend 40 minutes on this task.

*if you were born in **December** write a mini-essay about “Nowadays, the demand for private cars is increasing and it has led to a rise in pollution levels in many cities.”

Conclusion

This research paper evaluates students' knowledge in class by covering productive and receptive reading and writing skills. Considering the needs of my threshold-level learners, I have incorporated various methods into these assessments, making reading and writing skills the focus. The reading process encompasses both micro and macro skills and represents observable skills. Brown (2014) emphasizes that a broad range of reading strategies may be evaluated as part of the reading assessment process. Items that require students to learn and apply a variety of reading methods, like skimming and scanning, identifying discourse markers, determining word meanings from context, and using schemata to comprehend texts, are indicative of this.

“Reading is not directly observable; therefore, reading assessments are based indirectly on what are commonly believed to be the component subskills. The assessment focus was on skimming an entire passage for gist comprehension and identifying main ideas and supporting details” (Hubley, 2012, p.2)

Furthermore, the writing part is also closely connected to the reading assessment which encompasses the environmental sustainability in air and water. It is clear that students will be assessed in this part with the former knowledge of pollution to express their ideas on paper. Weigle (2012) noted that designing effective writing assessments, and considering how task variations can influence performance is crucial. He identifies a range of dimensions that differentiate writing assessment tasks. These include factors like the subject matter, the prompt type (bare prompt, reading passage, etc.), the cognitive demands, response time, prompt choice availability, and writing format (paper or computer). Research shows that prompt type impacts student performance. Therefore, identifying the key variable in a given situation is crucial.

This integrated skills assessment targets B1+ learners by focusing on core skills at this level. The chosen rubrics offer specific feedback while promoting communication effectiveness. According to Ayhan (2015), analytic rubrics are often used for large-scale assessments focused on general language proficiency. However, they can be just as valuable in the classroom when adapted to specific tasks such as writing. Barkaoui (2007 as cited in Weigle, 2012) thoroughly analyses essay test literature, highlighting that most research focuses on how writing assignments, the characteristics of the written work, and rater attributes impact test results. Traditionally, the focus of evaluation was on the qualities of the essay itself, such as grammar, organization, and clarity. The effects of the task and rater were seen as variables that needed to be controlled to ensure reliable scoring.

Although every test taker has different obstacles, each should be given accommodations based on a case-by-case analysis. For instance, there is a fairly wide range of hearing loss, even though the deaf and hard of hearing are sometimes lumped together: from people who have never heard to people who have lost their ability to hear, and from people who can hear with amplification but may not hear well to people who are profoundly deaf. From the point of disabled students, I consider that providing differentiation instruction in class releases challenges even if it is a minor. Still, this can be hard to feel in class as these disabled students. Therefore, differentiating instruction based on learners' individual needs fosters an inclusive learning environment that supports disabled students' academic success. As the point of writing assessment, I used differentiation instruction for deaf students by giving cards according to their birth month, as they get their cards they don't consider that the tasks are different from others which might create a good fair atmosphere during the assessment. Also, while creating visual materials for assessment “Visme” program is used.

Goldin-Meadow and Mayberry (2001, as cited in Taylor, 2016, p.11) A less obvious area requiring accommodation for deaf and hard-of-hearing students is the presentation of reading components in tests. They report that while a tiny number of profoundly deaf children acquire fluency in reading, the majority read poorly. Early readers who are deaf or hard of hearing, in particular, process material differently and more slowly than their hearing peers. Providing extended response time and accompanying pauses to combat test fatigue is an accepted accommodation.

Additionally, these assessments need ongoing updates while being used in lessons. While working on this project, I encountered challenges in creating a rubric for my learners. For this reason, I would like to develop special rubrics and assessment types tailored to both simple and disabled learners.

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